

HIGH RATE FRACTURE TOUGHNESS TEST DESIGN FOR TENSILE FIBRE FAILURE MODES

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SUMMARY

The compact tension specimen has been investigated numerically for the measurement of Mode I fracture toughness associated with fibre tensile failure, G_{Ic} , at crack speeds of the order of 200 m/s. This paper develops a load-independent data reduction scheme for analysing such tests using the compressive strain measured at the back edge of the specimen.

Keywords: Composites, Finite Element Analysis, Fracture Mechanics, Crack Growth, Dynamic Fracture

INTRODUCTION

Generally, the quasi-static (QS) properties of high-performance, fibre-reinforced, polymer-matrix composites are well-defined and consequently accurate models can be developed and designs refined before full-scale tests are carried out, reducing cost and time to market. However at high strain rates (HSRs) their behaviour is less clearly defined and, in some cases, unknown.

An understanding of the behaviour of composite materials at high rates is important as they are increasingly applied to components where their properties at HSRs are key to their purpose, such as armour plating for armoured personnel carriers, areas on aircraft likely to be subject to bird strike and impact-absorbing structures in cars.

A knowledge of the rate dependence of fracture toughnesses measured at high crack growth rates is particularly important for cases involving crack propagation. Three key issues arise consistently in the determination of fracture toughness at high displacement rates [1]:

- (i) Inertia effects are significant when the load changes suddenly and/or there is rapid crack growth.
- (ii) Rapid changes in load or crack growth can produce stress waves which affect the crack tip stress/strain field and therefore the failure process.
- (iii) Material properties, which may be used in data reduction, can exhibit strain rate dependence.

In the early stages of loading the energy release rate, G , can vary greatly due to stress wave interference (constructive and destructive) resulting in a highly complex, time dependent stress distribution in the specimen. The instantaneous value of G depends on the magnitude of the stress waves which pass through the crack tip region at a particular time. Therefore, if these stress waves are significant then G cannot be determined from the applied loads. [2]

Previous work in measuring the fracture toughness of laminated, polymer-matrix composites at high loading rates has focused on interlaminar fracture toughness, i.e. not involving tensile fibre failure. Blackman [3, 4], for example, used a standard DCB specimen loaded in a high-rate Instron machine. Blackman tested unidirectional carbon-fibre/epoxy composite bonded with epoxy paste, EA 9309, or epoxy film, FM73M. High-speed cameras allowed accurate determination of the displacement of the load point of the specimen. Using this setup tests at applied displacement rates up to 15 m/s were carried out, reaching peak crack speeds of 200 m/s.

A load-independent data reduction scheme was developed for these tests as the load measured was significantly affected by dynamic effects. This scheme assumed the displacement profile of the specimen tested at high rate (HR) was the same as the QS profile. This implies that the stress state at the crack tip is not significantly affected by asymmetry of the deformed shape (due to inertia effects) or stress waves. Previous work has shown [2], however, that this may not be suitable for the measurement of high-rate Mode I fracture toughness, G_{Ic} , because of the significant Mode II component which is induced due to the asymmetric deformation. This behaviour could be largely avoided by loading this specimen in a symmetric manner and highlights that mode-mixity at the crack tip must be considered when designing any experimental setup for measuring fracture toughness at high loading rate.

Figure 1: Compact Tension (CT) specimen [7]

The DCB specimen is not suitable, however, for measuring fracture toughness involving tensile fibre failure. Pinho et al [5] used the compact tension (CT) specimen, Fig. 1, to measure QS intralaminar fracture toughness of T300/913 carbon-epoxy laminated composite. The layup used was (90,0)_{8S} where the 0° direction is the direction of loading.

Data reduction was carried out using an Abaqus model to calculate the J-integral, J , for a 1 mm thick specimen with a crack of length a when a 1 N load was applied. The normalized energy release rate was then calculated as $f(a)$, Eq. 1:

$$f(a) = J \cdot \left(\frac{1\text{mm}}{1\text{N}} \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

$f(a)$ was then approximated by a third order polynomial and G_{Ic} of the laminate was obtained as Eq. 2:

$$G_{Ic} = \left(\frac{P}{t} \right)^2 f(a) \quad (2)$$

where P is the applied load in Newtons and t the thickness in mm of the specimen.

At higher loading rates, the CT specimen has been used to measure the fracture toughness of polymers, steel and short-fibre composites. Most of these studies have focused on loading rates well below 1 m/s or using split Hopkinson pressure bar. For the research described in this research it the use of the CT specimen at loading rates greater than 1 m/s that is of most interest.

Gensler et al [6] tested transparent, isotactic polypropylene at test rates between 0.1 mm/sec and 14 m/s using a standard CT specimen, loaded as in Fig. 1. Beguelin et al [7] also tested the CT specimen at test rates between 1 m/s and 7 m/s on epoxy resin. In both studies dynamic effects were limited by placing a damping material between the ram and the specimen to reduce the contact stiffness. Isochromatic fringes were recorded during the tests using a high-speed camera to show that a static stress state was present in those specimens loaded with low acceleration. At these low accelerations the stress distribution within the specimen was symmetrical about the crack plane and so the crack was progressing under pure Mode I conditions. This meant that the specimen could be analysed in the same way as a QS specimen – using the load measurement. The critical stress intensity factor, K_{Ic} , was then calculated using Eq. 3:

$$K_{Ic} = f \frac{P}{tW^{1/2}} \quad (3)$$

Where f is a geometrical factor which depends on a/W , P is the applied load, t is the specimen thickness and W the specimen width, as shown in Figure 1.

Applying too much damping during an experiment could over-damp the load-displacement trace, while too little will not remove the dynamic oscillations in the load. It is very difficult to apply the correct amount of damping and so it is preferable to have a data reduction scheme for HR CT tests in composite materials, which does not rely on the load measured during the test. This paper investigates the use of the CT specimen for testing laminated composites at high rates of loading and a data reduction scheme which is independent of the applied load is proposed.

FINITE ELEMENT MODEL DESCRIPTION

The HR CT test was investigated using LS-Dyna, an explicit finite element code. A CT model was created to represent the experimental setup and specimen dimensions used by Pinho et al [5], Fig. 2. (The dimensions of this specimen are as shown previously in Figure 1.) The model used material properties for IM7-8552 carbon-fibre epoxy [8] composite with a layup of $[(90,0)_8,90]_s$.

Figure 2: Schematic of CT model setup

The specimen was modelled using 8-noded brick elements. High order elements were used for a small region at the rear of the specimen (next to the cohesive element region) and around the loading pins, as well as the loading pins themselves in order to suppress the hour-glassing problems that were found to initiate in these regions. Laminate material properties, calculated from the unidirectional material properties using laminate theory, for the specimen are given in Table 1.

The elements used to model the behaviour of the interface were bi-linear cohesive elements detailed in [10]. The maximum interface element length was 0.17 mm ensuring that at least four elements were within the cohesive zone, so avoiding spurious oscillations in the load-displacement response of the model.

The value of Mode I fracture toughness input into the interface elements was 86 kJ/m^2 , which is the average value of G_{Ic} measured in the QS experiments. All models,

irrespective of test rate, used the same value of G_{Ic} . The maximum traction, N , in Mode I was 700 MPa – the failure strength of the laminate calculated from the unidirectional material properties using laminate theory and the maximum stress failure criteria. The penalty stiffness $k_{pos} = k_{neg} = 3.3 \times 10^4 \text{ N/mm}^3$ is a value typical of those that has been used in other studies.

Table 1: Input parameters for DCB model.

Parameter		Value
Density [9]	ρ [kg/m ³]	1570
Young's modulus	E_x [GPa], (out-of plane)	8.6
	E_y [GPa]	88.0669
	E_z [GPa]	97.9953
Poisson's ratio	ν_{yx}	0.42
	ν_{zx}	0.42
	ν_{zy}	0.34
Shear Modulus	G_{xy} [GPa]	3.496
	G_{yz} [GPa]	4.48
	G_{zx} [GPa]	3.496

The displacement was applied to the specimen at the centre-point of each end of the top loading pin by means of an applied velocity in the z -direction. The load points were constrained so that they were free to move in the z -direction only and free to rotate about any axis. The centre-point of each end of the lower pin was constrained in the x -, y - and z -directions but was free to rotate. No other support conditions were applied in the model. A surface-to-surface contact with a penalty stiffness based algorithm was implemented between the pins and the specimen.

The model was tested at a range of velocities from QS to 20 m/s.

QS models were run at 0.1 m/s with a combination of mass scaling and damping used to ensure that the kinetic energy was less than 1 % of the total – made up of kinetic, strain, hourglass energies and energy absorbed by damping. It was also important to ensure that the hourglass energy and the energy absorbed by damping was less than 10 % of the strain energy of the model. At higher displacement rates no mass-scaling or damping were implemented as these would affect the dynamic behaviour of the specimen.

The applied velocity profile is shown in Fig. 3. Using a model run without the velocity ramp, the value of t_{test} was found as the time at which the all the cohesive elements had completely failed. Using this, the duration of the velocity ramp was calculated as $1/10 t_{test}$. This initial ramp removes the vibrations in the load trace associated with the large forces which arise when the test velocity is applied without the ramp. This is particularly important at higher test velocities.

Figure 3: Velocity profile for CT model [4]

FINITE ELEMENT RESULTS

QS Model Validation

The load-displacement trace from the QS model is shown in Fig. 4 along with a theoretical curve. The theoretical curve was calculated using a linear Abaqus FE model by finding the applied load and displacement to ensure that the energy release rate was equal to G_{Ic} for a variety of crack lengths.

Figure 4: LS-Dyna QS model output compared with Abaqus prediction

HR Results

The load-displacement curve from the CT specimen loaded at 10 m/s is shown in Fig. 5. Loading at this rate corresponds to an average crack speed of 182.9 m/s between initiation, $a_0 = 26$ mm, and $a = 40$ mm. Due to the dynamic effects discussed previously, the onset of crack growth cannot be clearly deduced from this curve and the fracture toughness cannot readily be deduced from the applied load.

Figure 5: Load-displacement output of LS-Dyna model loaded at 10 m/s

The stresses in the model were investigated to establish whether any other failure mechanism could occur during the test. The failure mechanisms considered were compression at the back face of the specimen (FM1), compression of the specimen arms (FM2), matrix cracking due to in-plane shear stresses (FM3) or bearing (FM4) or shear (FM5) failure in the loading holes (Fig. 6). Only at a test speed of 10 m/s was laminate failure predicted (FM1 in Fig. 6) at a late stage in the test.

Figure 6: Failure mechanism locations in CT specimen

HR DATA REDUCTION PROPOSAL

In the previous section it was shown that it is not possible to use the applied load to determine the fracture toughness of the CT specimen loaded at high rate. Therefore another method of data reduction must be found. This section outlines a new method of calculating the fracture toughness in CT specimens loaded at high displacement rates.

Fig. 7 shows the z -direction compressive strain, ε_B at the back edge of the CT specimen versus the crack length for both the QS model and those loaded at 10 m/s. From this

figure it can be concluded that the effect of inertia and of stress waves within the specimen is very small – contributing to a 0.91 % decrease in strain from the QS to the 10 m/s model from initiation, $a = 0$ mm, to $a = 36$ mm. At 10 m/s this corresponds to an average crack velocity of 250 m/s. The other reason for the similarity of the HR and QS curves of Figure 7 is, of course, because the same intralaminar toughness has been used in the FE model. If, in reality, the toughness and/or the stiffness parameters are rate dependent then the experimentally observed ε_B versus a curves will not be the same for the HR and QS tests.

Figure 7: Strain at the back edge of CT specimen for both QS and HR model

It is proposed to use the FE-predicted ε_B versus a data and the associated loads to enable the HR toughness to be determined from the experimental ε_B versus a data. Using the QS model data the ratio, $k(a)$, of the applied load, $P_{B,QS}$, to the strain, $\varepsilon_{B,QS}$, measured close to the back edge of the specimen, can be determined as a function of crack length, a :

$$k(a) = \frac{P_{B,QS}(a)}{\varepsilon_{B,QS}(a)} \quad (4)$$

An equivalent load, $\bar{P}_{HR}(a)$, for the specimen loaded at HR can then be determined from the experimentally observed strain, $\varepsilon_{B,HR}$, and crack length as:

$$\bar{P}_{HR}(a) = k(a) \cdot \varepsilon_{B,HR}(a) \quad (5)$$

The value of HR fracture toughness can then be determined by using the compliance calibration:

$$G = \frac{P^2}{2t} \frac{dC}{da} \quad (6)$$

where C is the compliance of the specimen. Substituting $\bar{P}_{HR}(a)$ for P from Eq. 5 gives:

$$G_{Ic,HR} = \frac{k^2(a) \cdot \varepsilon_{B,HR}^2}{2t} \cdot \frac{dC}{da} \quad (7)$$

where $G_{Ic,HR}$ is the HR Mode I intralaminar fracture toughness of the specimen, $k(a)$ is calculated using Eq. 4, $\varepsilon_{B,HR}$ is the strain measured at the back surface of the specimen for a given crack length in the HR model and t the thickness of the specimen in the x -direction. Assuming the compliance of the specimen for a given crack length is the same in both the QS and HR (i.e. there is no rate dependences of the stiffness properties) models then dC/da can be calculated from the QS model.

Fig. 8 shows the ratio of $G_{Ic,HR} / G_{Ic,Input}$ calculated using Eq. 7 using the predictions of $\varepsilon_{B,HR}$ for the specimens loaded at 5 m/s and 10 m/s. From Fig. 8 it can be seen that the percentage error in the results is a increase of 6 % from the QS to the 10 m/s models for crack lengths between 26 mm and 36 mm.

Figure 8: $G_{HR}/G_{Ic,input}$ versus a for the specimen loaded at 10 m/s

If, therefore, during experimental testing the HR value is measured to be significantly greater than 6% higher than the QS value then the result would indicate that the G_{Ic} is rate dependent.

CONCLUSION

The use of the CT specimen for determining the Mode I intralaminar fracture toughness of composites at QS test rates is well documented and the results understood and accepted. The current work has shown that the CT specimen is suitable for testing at higher applied displacement rates. A finite element model of the CT specimen has been

developed and it has been shown that for the geometry and material considered intralaminar crack growth will occur in the absence of any other failure mode for applied displacement rates of almost 10 m/s.

Dynamic effects mean, however, that the results cannot be analysed in the same way as for QS results, using the load-crack length data. A data reduction scheme has been outlined which does not require the measurement of the load during the high rate tests. Strain at the back edge of the specimen and the crack length are measured in HR tests which allows the Mode I fracture toughness to be calculated. The FE analyses indicate that at 10 m/s an increase in G_{Ic} of more than 6 % compared to QS value suggests a significant change in fracture toughness with test rate.

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